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Portfolio Mix And Financial Performance Of Deposit Money Bank In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the portfolio mix and financial performance of deposit money bank. The objectives of this study are to; examine the effect of equity on financial performance of deposit money bank; assess the effect of bonds on financial performance of deposit money bank; investigate the effect of Treasury bill on financial performance of deposit money bank; examine the effect of credit to private sector on financial performance of deposit money bank. Four research questions and four hypotheses were formulated in line with the stated objectives. The variables used were sourced of from secondary source. Ex-post facto research design was used in this study, the study selected investment firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Listing (NEL) while, the study used panel least square as a method of data analysis. The variables used are equity, bonds, credit to private sector and treasury bills. The study finds out equity has negative and insignificant effect on financial performance. Bonds have positive and insignificant effect on financial performance. Treasury bill has positive and significant effect on financial performance. Credit to private sector has positive and significant effect on financial performance. The study recommends that Shareholders should provide the support that will induce greater entrepreneurial and investments effectiveness/efficiency in harnessing available portfolio investment in equity to promote income generation, poverty alleviation, job creation and inclusive financial performance and development in Nigeria. Also, concerted efforts should be made by policy makers to increase the level of participation in treasury bills and also make the yield more attractive to investors.

Keywords: portfolio mix, financial performance, bonds, Treasury bill, equity

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

The process of spreading an investment across assets through the vehicle of constructing portfolio is called diversification. According to Valentine, Victor and Chidera, (2020) portfolio diversification is one of the most important lessons from capital market theory. Although endless theoretical and empirical debates have occurred over whether beta and other factors drive asset returns, there is little disagreement that diversification is a worthwhile activity (Ogbanja, & Chukwumere, 2024).

Portfolio mix (PM) as wide range of assets classes, such as stocks, government bonds, corporate bonds, treasury bills, real estate investment trusts, exchange traded funds, mutual funds, certificates of deposit. It also includes options, warrants and other derivatives such as futures, and physical investments like commodities, real estate, land and timber (Onuorah, Akujuobi & Linus, 2013).

Portfolio investment refers to economic transactions in highly liquid financial assets, such as stocks and bonds. It is an investment in the equity of a company made by individuals who have no stake in the running and administration of the company (Onyekachi, & Onyeyibo, 2024). This type of investment is usually compared with direct investment, which requires the actual mobilization of productive resources

by the prospective foreign investors. Meanwhile, as large capital outlay requirement, long gestation period and most importantly the risk averse nature of most investors have been the major deterrents to direct investment, portfolio investment has gained much prominence especially among middle income risk averse investors (Pflug, Pitchler, & Wozabel, 2024).

Investment in stocks and other associated investments is usually fraught with risk. We invest to earn a return by channeling money or other resources in the expectation of reaping future benefits. The concern of most investors is how to maximize returns while minimizing risk. This is not unconnected with the natural tendency for man to loath risk. In other to achieve this, Markowitz in his path breaking study initiated the idea of portfolio diversification as a strategy for dealing with the concerns of investors about risk and returns. The difficulty with Markowitz diversification is the level of sophistication and tedious computations involved in selecting assets for inclusion in portfolios. This is because Markowitz diversification involves the combining of assets that are less than perfectly positively correlated in order to reduce risk without sacrificing any of the portfolio returns (Naomi & Michael, 2021).

Talmud, which is a variant of Naïve strategy, offered a simple rule for diversification otherwise known as 1/N rule. As in Pflug (2012), the 1/N investment strategy involves splitting assets uniformly among available suitable investment possibilities. They went further to say that, an asset allocation strategy as simple as the rule to divide available capital evenly among some (or even all) investment opportunities falls short of sophistication of modern portfolio theory which in broad terms states that a portfolio should strike optimal balance between prospective return of an investment and the possible risks of investing. The optimal decision depends on the risk preferences of the investor. For instance, Markowitz says, he used 1/N rule himself on psychological ground when he answered the question on how he manages his own funds by saying: “my intention was to maximize my future regret. So I split my contribution fifty-fifty between bonds and equities” (Valentine, Victor & Chidera, 2020).

The classical theory of portfolio choice rests on strong assumptions as no transaction costs, investor’s awareness of menu of asset available and knowledge of their risk and return, no uninsurable risks, such as human capital. If all investors face same distribution of returns and had same information set, in equilibrium they selected the same menu of risky assets (Sannassee, Seetanah & Lamport, 2014). of the adverse shock on the portfolio is otherwise mitigated (Nwakiri & Okoroyibo, 2021).

1.2 Statement of Problem

The problem of this research work stems out of the fact that the Nigerian business environment is highly uncertain with inconsistencies in government policies and non-transparency of government operations which has led to the discouragement of foreign investors from investing in the Nigerian stock market. Adding to this problem, inflows of portfolio investment into Nigeria may have been limited by the infancy of Nigerian capital and money market, although the markets have witness growth and development in recent years but are still not yet as huge, vibrant and sophisticated as their counterpart in the industrialized nations and as such, cannot compete favorably with them for investment funds. Also, low interest rates in developed countries is push factor and financial liberalization programs in developing countries is pull factor for increasing international portfolio investments. Regrettably, Nigeria is still battling with unstable economic condition coupled with several challenges such as high level of poverty rate, low capacity utilization, declining output level, increasing unemployment rates, unstable power supply and decay in infrastructure among others, (Edu, Inaya & Basse, 2015). The cogent factors attributed to these challenges are conducive business environment and unfavourable policies formulated that hinder the flows of foreign investment capitals. Irrespective of the effectiveness of capital market, weak legal system coupled with poor business environment may hinder foreign investment inflows. Nigeria’s business environment is also characterized by poor power supply, insecurity, poor infrastructure as well as weak and slow judicial process coupled with non-transparency of government operations. Consequent upon these highlighted problems, this study investigates the relationship between foreign portfolio investment and the growth of Nigerian economy.

Different empirical studies have been conducted on the effect of portfolio diversification on financial performance in Nigeria with conflicting results and conclusions in respect of positive and negative effect on the economy. Such Works were (Onyekachi & Onyeyibo, 2020; Ogbanja, & Chukwumere, 2021;

Nwakiri, & Okoroyibo, 2021, Okafor, Ezeaku and Izuchukwu, (2015), Okafor, Ugwuegbe and Ezeaku, (2016). This tends to suggest that there are still inconsistencies in empirical findings on the subject. These conflicting findings can be partly attributed to different types of econometrics methodologies adopted in such empirical studies. This shortcoming has created a knowledge gap in literature which this study seeks to close.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to investigate the effect of portfolio mix on financial performance of deposit money bank. The following are other specific objectives to:

1. Examine the effect of equity on financial performance of deposit money bank.
2. Assess the effect of bonds on financial performance of deposit money bank.
3. Investigate the effect of Treasury bill on financial performance of deposit money bank.
4. Examine the effect of on financial performance of deposit money bank.

1.4 Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

- H₀₁:** Equity has no significant effect on financial performance of deposit money bank.
H₀₂: Bonds has no significant effect on financial performance of deposit money bank.
H₀₃: Treasury bile has no significant effect on financial performance of deposit money bank.
H₀₄: Credit to private sector has no significant effect on financial performance of deposit money bank.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Portfolio Mix

A portfolio mix refers to the strategic combination of different asset classes, investment instruments, or business components that an individual, organization, or firm holds in order to achieve specific financial, operational, or strategic objectives (Sa'adu, Hussaini & Ibrahim 2016). It represents how resources are allocated across multiple options such as stocks, bonds, cash, real estate, products, markets, or business units with the aim of balancing risk, return, stability, and growth. In finance, a portfolio mix typically includes the proportion of equities, fixed income securities, money market instruments, alternative investments, and tangible assets. The mix is carefully designed based on factors such as the investor's risk tolerance, investment horizon, financial goals, market conditions, and expected return (Otapo, 2021). A well-structured portfolio mix reduces exposure to risk through diversification, ensuring that poor performance in one category does not significantly harm overall performance. In business strategy, the concept of portfolio mix extends to how a company allocates resources among various products, services, business units, or markets (Paul, Chibueze & Callistus, 2016). This helps managers evaluate which areas require investment, restructuring, maintenance optimization, or divestment, thereby supporting long-term competitiveness and sustainable growth. Overall, a portfolio mix is a deliberate and dynamic allocation approach that helps balance risks and opportunities while improving financial or business performance. It evolves over time in response to changing economic conditions, organizational strategy, and performance outcomes.

2.1.2 Financial performance

Financial performance is defined by Antwi, Mills, and Zhao, (2013), as the process that brings about increase in the real per capita income of a country over a long period of time. Also, Barro, and Martin, (1992), defined financial performance as a steady process by which the productive capacity of the economy is increased over time to bring about rising levels of national output and income. Sabir, and Tahir, (2012), defined financial performance as the increasing capacity of the economy to satisfy the wants of goods and services of the members of society.

Financial performance means an increase in the capacity of an economy to produce goods and services, compared from one period of time to another. Financial performance is a process by which a nation wealth increases over time. The most widely used measures of financial performance is the rate of growth in a country's total output of goods and services gauged by the gross domestic product (GDP). Financial performance can also be referred to as the increase of gross domestic product (GDP) or other measures of

aggregate income, typically reported as the annual rate of change in the real GDP. According to Aigbokhan (1995), financial performance means an increase in the average rate of output produce per person usually measured on a per annum basic. It is also the rate of change in national output or income in a given period. Financial performance is the increase in gross domestic product (GDP) or other measure of aggregate income. It is often measured as the rate of change in real GDP. Financial performance refers only to the quantity of goods and services produced. Edoumiekumo and Opukri (2013) define financial performance as an increase in performance (GDP). That is, gross domestic product adjusted for inflation. The growth can either be positive or negative. Negative growth can be referred to by saying that the economy is shrinking. This is characterized with economic recession and economic depression. Ullah and Rauf (2013) noted that whenever there is increase in real GDP of a country it will boost up the overall output and we called it financial performance. The financial performance is helpful to increase the incomes of the society, help the nation to bring the unemployment at low level and also helpful in the deliveries of public services.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored on the modern portfolio theory (MPT) by Harry Markowitz (1952)

MPT is an investment framework for the selection and construction of investment portfolios based on the maximization of expected returns of the portfolio and the simultaneous minimization of investment risk. Overall, the risk component of MPT can be measured, using various mathematical formulations, and reduced via the concept of diversification which aims to properly select a weighted collection of investment assets that together exhibit lower risk factors than investment in any individual asset or singular asset class. Diversification is, in fact, the core concept of MPT and directly relies on the conventional wisdom of "never putting all your eggs in one basket". It is instructive to note here that Markowitz' portfolio selection theory is a normative theory. Conversely, Sharpe's asset pricing theory (CAPM) is regarded as a positive theory one that hypothesizes how investors actually behave as opposed to how they should behave. Together, they provide a theoretical to how they should behave. Together, they provide a theoretical 103 framework for the identification and measurement of investment risk and the development of relationships between expected return and risk. This analysis assumes that MPT is indeed independent of asset pricing theory, with the latter concept the subject of separate analysis. The framework for IPT (international portfolio theory) includes numerous assumptions about markets and investors. Some of these assumptions are explicit, while others are implicit. Markowitz built his portfolio selection contributions to MPT on the following key assumptions. i.) Investors are rational (they seek to maximize returns while minimizing risk). ii.) Investors are only willing to accept higher amounts of risk if they are compensated by higher expected returns.

iii.) Investors timely receive all pertinent information related to their investment decision, iv.) Investors can borrow or lend an unlimited amount of capital at a risk free rate of interest, v.) Markets are perfectly efficient. vi.) Markets do not include transaction costs or taxes. vii.) It is possible to select securities whose individual performance is independent of other portfolio investments. These foundational assumptions of international portfolio theory have been widely challenged.

Relevance to the study

The modern portfolio theory (MPT) is a practical method for selecting investments in order to maximize their overall returns within an acceptable level of risk. This mathematical framework is used to build a portfolio of investments that maximize the amount of expected return for the collective given level of risk.

2.3 Empirical Review

Otapo, (2021) studied the dynamic nature of the development of the relationship between foreign investment and economic growth in Nigeria from 1980 to 2018. The use of the Augmented-Dickey Fuller test confirmed the precondition for adopting dynamic techniques to test the significant role of foreign portfolio investment (among other analyzed factors – domestic savings, government capital expenditures, market capitalization) in the formation of gross domestic product. The use of the lag selection method allowed to determine the optimal lag for estimating the autoregressive distributed model, which substantiates the effectiveness and reliability of the autoregressive distributed lag model. The information

base of the study was the statistical bulletin of the Central Bank of Nigeria. The study empirically confirms and theoretically proves that foreign investment, domestic savings, government spending and market capitalization determine long-term trends in gross domestic product formation in Nigeria. Practically, the empirical result revealed that the presence of a significant deficit of domestic savings in Nigeria creates obstacles to successful economic growth in the country both in the short and long term; portfolio foreign investment accelerates economic growth in the long run to a greater extent than in the short run.

Ejike, (2021) assesses portfolio diversification in equity and Nigerian economy for the period 2015 to 2020. The study applied equity capital, preference capital, Long-term loan, debentures to measure equity financing while gross domestic product were used as the dependent variable. The data was analyzed using pooled ordinary least square, fixed effect and random effect regression technique. The results of the analysis divulged that portfolio diversification in equity had significantly and positively improved Nigerian economy

Ogbanja and Chukwumere, (2021) empirically evaluated the effect of portfolio investment diversification in equity on economic growth in Nigeria. Using secondary data for the period 2001 to 2018. The data on equity capital, preference capital, Long-term loan, debentures were employed and analyzed with econometric technique involving descriptive statistics and multiple regression analysis using the E-view computer software for analyzing data. The results of analysis revealed that portfolio investment diversification had significant positive influence on real gross domestic product positive effect on economic growth in Nigeria

Nwakiri and Okoroyibo, (2021) investigated portfolio diversification in equity and economic growth in Nigeria from 2000 to 2019. The study employed the Bounds Co-integration test and the Error Correction Model (ECM) to analyze the relationship between equity capital, preference capital and debt capital and real gross domestic product. The result of the study showed that Portfolio diversification in equity has positive effects on economic growth in Nigeria in the long and the short run. The relative insignificance is however attributed to the low level of portfolio diversity in equity at the in Nigeria

Naomi and Michael (2021) employed the Bounds Co-integration test and the Error Correction Model (ECM) under the Autoregressive Distributed Lags (ARDL) model framework and found that indeed, export diversification has positive, though insignificant effect on economic growth in Nigeria in the long and the short run. The relative insignificance is however attributed to the low level of diversity of exports at the moment; implying that greater diversity should see it have significant effects on growth.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The study employed the *ex-post-facto* research design to investigate the effect of portfolio diversification on financial performance in Nigeria. The use of *ex-post facto research design* is appropriate for this study as the data were collected from an existing document which the researcher will not attempt to manipulate. A number of authors acknowledge this design as suitable when the data already exist and the researchers do not intend to change the state of the data (Onwumere, 2009; Kerlinger, 1973).

3.2 Nature and Sources of Data

The study used secondary data that were sourced from financial publications such as the Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE) Fact Book and Daily Official List. Central Bank of Nigeria, Statistical Bulletin, CBN Annual Reports and Accounts for the period under review

3.3 Model Specification

The model used for the study was the adaptation and modifications of the work of Ammara and Ahmad (2011) which examined the impact of return in a well diversified portfolio on financial performance in Nigeria.

$$GDPR = f(EQT, BND, TRB) \text{ -----(i)}$$

Where:

GDPR = Annual growth rate of gross domestic product

EQT= Equity

BND = Bonds

TRB = Treasury Bill

The modified model is stated thus:

$ROA = f(EQT, BND, TRB \text{ and } DIP)$

The Econometric Equation Form of the Model is:

$$ROA = \beta_0 + \beta_1EQT + \beta_2BND + \beta_3TRB + \beta_4DIP + \mu \text{ --- (ii)}$$

Where:

ROA = Return on Asset

EQT= Equity

BND = Bonds

TRB = Treasury Bill

CPS= Credit to private sector

β_0 and μ are the constant and error term respectively while $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ are the coefficient of Equity, bonds, treasury bill and credit to private sector on financial performance .

3.4 Method of data Analyses

The data were analyzed with econometric techniques Descriptive Statistics, Augmented Dickey Fuller Tests for Unit Roots and Ordinary Least Square (OLS). The OLS method of data analysis was done through the instrumentality of Econometric View (E-view 9) as statistical software. The technique (OLS) was employed because it has the criteria of being Best Linear Unbiased Estimator of linear relationship.

3.4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics are introductory analyses that explained the normality of the variables used for the analyses. The statistics include the mean, median, minimum and maximum, standard deviation and Jacque Bera tests. Mean is the average value of the series, obtained by adding up the series and dividing by the number of observations. Median is the middle value (or average of the two middle values) of the series when the values are ordered from the smallest to the largest. The median is a robust measure of the centre of the distribution that is less sensitive to outliers than the mean.

Maximum and Minimum are the maximum and minimum values of the series in the current sample. Std Dev. (standard deviation) is a measure of dispersion or spread in the series. Skewness is a measure of asymmetry of the distribution of the series around its mean. Kurtosis measures the peakiness or flatness of the distribution of the series. If the kurtosis exceeds 3, the distribution is peaked (leptokurtic) relative to the normal; if the kurtosis is less than 3, the distribution is flat (platykurtic) relative to the normal. Jarque-Bera is a test statistic for testing whether the series is normally distributed. The null hypotheses is that the variable is normally distributed.

Decision Rule

Decision rule is to reject when p. value is less than 0.05 level of significance

3.4.2 Unit Root Test

Given the fact that the study used time series data, it was worthwhile to test for stationarity of the data. Stationarity was tested by using Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root tests. According to Granger and Newbold (1974), if the variables under study are non-stationary then they may lead to unauthentic results, so it's important that the series of data is stationary. In this study the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test was applied to check the Stationarity of the variables.

Decision Rule

If $t^* >$ ADF critical value, then do not reject null hypotheses, i.e., unit root exists.

If $t^* <$ ADF critical value, then reject the null hypotheses, i.e., unit root does not exist.

We employed Ordinary Least Square (OLS) because the order of integration is at level

3.4.3 Ordinary Least Square (OLS)

The estimation of the models was done using Ordinary Least Square (OLS). The OLS employed because it has the criteria of being Best Linear Unbiased Estimator of linear relationship. The Coefficient of Determination (R^2) measures the explanatory power of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The r^2 normally makes an overestimation of the true value of the population especially when

small sample is used. The Adj r^2 correct this problem (Pallant, 2004). Therefore, since the sample is a small one, we used Adj r^2 .F-Test to measures the overall significance.

Student T-Test measures the individual significance of the estimated independent variables. The decision rule for test of hypotheses is to reject the null hypotheses for calculated significance value below 5% level of significance.

PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

Introduction

This chapter presents the empirical results and discussion of findings, Ordinary Least Square was used as techniques for the analysis, the result was subjected to different statistical and econometrics test. We begin by presenting the data for analysis and discussing the order of integration of the interest variables. The data for the analysis will be seen in the appendix1

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics for Portfolio Mix and performance

	ROA	BND	EQT	CPS	TRB
Mean	17956.69	181.8653	4586.165	6916.003	1075.413
Median	4350.315	6.850000	1626.100	1259.100	642.9700
Maximum	89043.62	1400.430	14956.59	26934.77	3579.800
Minimum	144.8300	0.000000	4.000000	21.08000	24.13000
Std. Dev.	25929.83	394.0638	5171.576	8944.721	1133.813
Skewness	1.476472	2.529421	0.649871	0.970616	0.867446
Kurtosis	3.934800	8.022032	1.853551	2.406026	2.246586
Jarque-Bera	13.59112	71.98463	4.255206	5.838344	5.068104
Probability	0.001119	0.000000	0.119122	0.053978	0.079337
Sum	610527.4	6183.420	155929.6	235144.1	36564.05
Sum Sq. Dev.	2.22E+10	5124447.	8.83E+08	2.64E+09	42422564
Observations	34	34	34	34	34

Source: Researcher computation (2025)

The descriptive statistics showed the mean and standard deviation. The mean is the average value of each variable over the years while the standard deviation shows the variability of the values. The descriptive statistics also showed the maximum and minimum values. The Jarque-Bera statistics is the test of normality of the time series variables.

The variables of the study shown on Table 2 above indicate that the annual growth rate of gross domestic product has mean of 17956.69 with minimum value of 144.8300 and maximum values of 89043.62 respectively. However, the standard deviation is 2.59% indicating low variation in the return on assets (ROA). This means that the Nigerian economy is relatively unpredictable and risky. This is capable of discouraging investment in the country. Results of the descriptive statistics showed that Bonds had a mean of 181.8653 and standard deviation of 394.0638 with minimum and maximum values of 0.000000 and 1400.430 respectively

Equity had a mean of 4586.165, with standard deviation of 5171.576 with minimum and maximum values of 4.000000 and 14956.59 respectively. Treasury Bill had a mean of 1075.413 with standard deviation of 1133.813 with minimum and maximum values of 24.13000 and 3579.800 respectively. Credit to private sector had a mean of 6916.003 with standard deviation of 8944.721 with minimum and maximum values of 21.08000 and 26934.77 respectively. Since the P.values are greater than 0.05, the study cannot reject the null hypothesis that the model is normally distributed.

1.2 Unit Root Test

In literature, most time series variables are non-stationary and using non-stationary variables in the model might lead to spurious regressions. The first or second differenced terms of most variables will usually be stationary (Ramathan, 1992). The units roots test results in first differences using the augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) are presented in table 4.1 below. The result shows that the null hypothesis is accepted at level for all variables. This implies that most of the series are not stationary or integrated of order zero. Nigerian economy measured by logarithm of gross domestic product is not stationary at level but becomes stationary at first difference. The null hypothesis is rejected after differencing once. After differencing once, all the variables yield results that clearly show that the series is stationary. Therefore we conclude that variables are unmistakably integrated of order one. Below show the table summaries of the unit root test

Table 4.2 Unit Root Test

variable	ADF	Integration	Significant
ROA	-5.009605	1(1)	1%
CPS	-6.494927	1(1)	1%
BND	-5.112904	1(1)	1%
TRB	-4.583766	1(1)	1%
EXD	-6.073415	1(1)	1%

Source: Author's computation (2025)

Finally, the ADF test was conducted on the effect of portfolio diversification on financial performance of Nigeria from 2013 to 2023, and the results presented in table 4.2 show that null hypothesis of unit roots was rejected after differencing twice. Hence, the variable is clearly integrated of order one and at 1% level of significant respectively.

1.3 Co-Integration test

Given that all the variables are integrated of order one, co-integration test was carried out to establish whether the variable though individually non-stationary could be co-integrated as a group and also to establish the existence of a long-run relationship among them. The Johansen procedure is used to achieve this. The results of this test are presented in Appendix. Both trace statistic and maximum eigenvalue test are used to determine the number of co-integrating vectors. The test statistic rejects the null hypothesis in favour of one co-integrating relationship at 5% significant level. But the maximum eigenvalue test indicates also two co-integrating relation at the 5% level. The long run coefficients emanating from the co-integration relationship normalization on the economy is presented in Table 4.3. The table 4.3 shows the summary of Mackinnon Haug-Michelis co-integration result.

Table 4.3: Johansen Co-integration Test

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)				
Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	Critical Value 0.05	Prob.**
None*	0.811775	116.6959	69.81889	0.0000
At most 1*	0.664714	64.92220	47.85613	0.0006
At most 2*	0.494832	31.04627	29.79707	0.0357
At most 3	0.272729	9.877488	15.49471	0.2903
At most 4	0.000173	0.005363	3.841466	0.9409
Trace test indicates 3 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level *denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level **Mackinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values				
Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)				
None*	0.552583	29.75777	28.58808	0.0353
At most 1	0.357826	16.38712	22.29962	0.2716
At most 2	0.179732	7.330577	15.89210	0.6290
At most 3	0.098687	3.844381	9.164546	0.4358
At most 4				
Max-eigenvalue test indicates 3 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level *denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level **Mackinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values				

Source: Author's Compilation (2025)

The result of Johansen co-integration test is shown in Table 4.2, the result shows that there exist one (1) co-integrating equations at 5% level of significance. This is because the trace statistic is greater than critical values at 5%. This shows that there exists a long run relationship between performance and all the explanatory variables. The result indicates that in the long run, the dependent variables can be efficiently anticipated using the specified independent variables and, thus, we proceeded to estimate the Error Correction Model (ECM) so as to reconcile the short-run dynamics with long-run disequilibrium of the variables. The Error Correction Model results are presented in table 4.3.

4.4 Regression Result

The full part of our regression result for this analysis is attached as an appendix to this study. However, the diagnostic tests or some key statistics or the variable that needs to be interpreted is shown in table 4.4.

Table 4.4 Error Correction Model Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std.error	T-test	Prob
C	0.819453	0.283986	2.885537	0.0078
LBND	0.004303	0.037324	0.115301	0.9091
LEQT	-0.137173	0.079282	-1.730188	0.0955
LCPS	0.871939	0.106662	8.174777	0.0000
LTRB	0.331257	0.084313	3.928916	0.0006
ECM(-1)	-0.762661	0.132703	-5.747142	0.0000

R-Squared: 0.893165; Adjusted R-squared: 0.881851 ;F-statistic: 75.56065; Prob(F-statistic): 0.000000; Durbin-Watson Stat: 1.900132

Source: Author's Compilation (2025)

The results presented above will be analyzed using three criteria; economic a priori criteria, statistical criteria and econometric criteria.

Economic a priori Criteria

The a priori expectation is used to determine the existing finance theories and this indicates the signs and magnitude of our variables. From the result in table 4.3, the result shows a regression line intercept of 0.819453. The value is positive and statistically significant 2.885537 with p-value of 0.0078 which is less than 0.05. Hence this is an indication that the GDP_r will be constant at 81.% per percent per annum when there is no change in the explanatory variables.

The regression result shown in Table 4.3, shows a positive relationship between portfolio diversification and performance. The value for bound is 0.004303; this implies that One percent increase in bound, ceteris paribus, will lead to about 43 percent increase in rate performance. This is consistent with apriori expectation. This result supports the fact that increasing bound enhances rate performance.

Equity has a negative correlation with gross domestic product. The value for Equity is -0.137173; this implies that One percent increase in equity ceteris paribus, will lead to about 11 percent increase in rate gross domestic product. This is consistent with apriori expectation. This result supports the fact that increase in bound improves the rate performance.

Credit to private sector has a positive correlation with rate performance. The value for Credit to private sector is 0.871939 this implies that One percent decrease in Credit to private sector, ceteris paribus, will lead to about 2 percent increase in performance in Nigeria. This is consistent with apriori expectation. This result supports the fact that increase credit to private sector will increase the performance.

Treasury bill has a positive correlation with rate performance. The value for Treasury bill is 0.331257 this implies that One percent decrease in Treasury bill, ceteris paribus, will lead to about 33 percent increase in rate of performance in Nigeria. This is consistent with apriori expectation. This result supports the fact that increase Treasury bill will increase the performance

Statistical Criteria

From the results obtained, the bound is revealed positive and statistically insignificant with their t- value and p-value of 0.115301 (0.9091). This is because their p-value was less than 5% level of significance. This result means that bounds is positive and has insignificant impact on rate of performance in Nigeria Equity has a positive and negative impact on performance in Nigeria. This was revealed through their t- value which is -1.730188 while the p-value of 0.0955 was less than 5 percent level of significance. This

result means that Equity has negative impact and has not translated to positive impact on firm performance.

The credit to private sector has a positive significant impact on performance in Nigeria. This was revealed through their t-value which is 8.174777 while the p-value of 0.0000 were less than 5 percent level of significance. This result means that dividend payout has significant effect on performance.

The Treasury bill has a positive significant impact on performance in Nigeria. This was revealed through their t-value which is 3.928916 while the p-value of 0.0006 were less than 5 percent level of significance. This result means that dividend payout has significant effect on performance.

From the result, the value of the coefficient of determination R^2 is 0.893165 which implies that 89% of the variation in performance is explained by the independent variables included in the model. While about 11 % are accounted for by variables outside our model. This further show that there is a high goodness of fit in the model

The *f*-statistics value of 75.56065 in the model, which are a measure of the joint significance of the explanatory variables, is found to be statistically significant at 1 percent level as indicated by the corresponding probability value of 0.000. This indicates that there is a significant differences between the dependent and independent variables.

Econometric Criterion

Finally, the Durbin Watson test of autocorrelation shows an absence of serial autocorrelation. This is because the calculated value of DW (1.900132) falls between lower critical level (DU) and 2 at 1% significant level. Where $DU = 2$. With this result we reject the hypothesis that there is presence of serial autocorrelation in our model. Therefore, parameter estimates from our model are stable, efficient suitable for policy simulation.

The result shows that the coefficient of ECM is negative -0.762661 and significant at 1% percent critical level. This shows that about 76 percent disequilibria in the performance in Nigeria in the previous years are corrected for in the current year. The significance of the ECM is an indication and a confirmation of the existence of a long run equilibrium relationship between performance and the independent variables used in this study. The robustness of the error correction method further buttresses that only 76 percent is corrected in the previous year.

4.5 Hypotheses Testing

The need to examine the relationship between the collected data and the stated hypothesis has called for this section. This result will be compared with the statistical criteria to see if the preconceived notion in thus research work holds or not. However, if the probability value is less than 0.05%, alternative hypothesis is accepted, but when it is greater than 5% null hypothesis is accepted

Hypothesis One

Ho₁: Equity has no significant effect on financial performance in Nigeria.

Decision Rule: However, if the probability value is less than 0.05%, alternative hypothesis is accepted, but when it is greater than 5% null hypothesis is accepted

From the result report of our t-test in table 4.4 above, it was observed from equity, the value is -1.730188 with the probability of 0.0955 which is less than the desired level of significant (0.005), we accept the null (Ho) which says that Equity has no significant effect on financial performance in Nigeria

Hypothesis Two

Ho₁: Bounds has no significant effect on financial performance in Nigeria.

Decision Rule: However, if the probability value is less than 0.05%, alternative hypothesis is accepted, but when it is greater than 5% null hypothesis is accepted

From the result report of our t-test in table 4.4 above, it was observed from bound, the value is 0.115301 with the probability of 0.9091 which is less than the desired level of significant (0.005), we accept the null (Ho) which says that equity has no significant effect on financial performance in Nigeria

Hypothesis Three

Ho₃: Treasury bill has no significant effect on financial performance.

Decision Rule: However, if the probability value is less than 0.05%, alternative hypothesis is accepted, but when it is greater than 5% hull hypothesis is accepted.

From table 4.4 above, we find out that computed value for Treasury bill is 3.928916 while its probability is 0.0006. This shows that the Treasury bill is statistically significant. Based on this analysis we reject (H₀) and accept (H₁), which implies that treasury bile has no significant effect on financial performance.

Hypothesis Four

H₀₄: Credit to private sector has no significant effect on financial performance

Decision Rule: However, if the probability value is less than 0.05%, alternative hypothesis is accepted, but when it is greater than 5% hull hypothesis is accepted.

From table 4.4 above, we find out that computed value for Credit to private sector is 8.174777 while its probability is 0.0000. This shows that the Credit to private sector is statistically significant. Based on this analysis we reject (H₀) and accept (H₁), which implies that Credit to private sector has no significant effect on financial performance

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Findings

The findings of the study are summarized as follows:

1. Equity has negative and insignificant effect on financial performance.
2. Bonds have positive and insignificant effect on financial performance
3. Treasury bill has positive and significant effect on financial performance
4. Credit to private has positive and significant effect on financial performance

5.2 Conclusion

The result of the study indicates that portfolio mix in equity, has negative and insignificant effect on financial performance of Nigeria, while bounds has positive and insignificant effect financial performance of Nigeria. Meanwhile credit to the private sector has positive and significant effect on gross domestic product; as well portfolio mix on treasury bills has positive and significant effect on performance in Nigeria within the period under study. The study thus concludes that, portfolio mix has a significant positive effect on financial performance.

5.3 Recommendations

The study recommends as follows:

Shareholders should provide the support that will induce greater entrepreneurial and investments effectiveness/efficiency in harnessing available portfolio investment in equity to promote income generation, poverty alleviation, job creation and inclusive financial performance and development in Nigeria

The macroeconomic environment, political and social environment should be made more conducive to sustain and encourage increase in portfolio investment in bonds as this will develop working and activity-driven agricultural, manufacturing and solid mineral sub-sectors for improved and sustainable financial performance and development in Nigeria

Concerted efforts should be made by policy makers to increase the level of participation in treasury bills and also make the yield more attractive to investors.

The monetary authorities in Nigeria should maintain a favorable interest rate ceiling between the lending and deposit rate as this will likely enhance investment activities in Nigeria

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